

Synthesis, Spectral Studies and Antimicrobial Activity of some Fluorine-containing 2-Amino-4-arylthiazoles

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Manuscript received 13 August 1993, revised 22 February 1995, accepted 15 June 1995

Thiazoles exhibit pharmacological and biological activities¹. The incorporation of fluorine in heterocyclic systems causes a profound change in biological activities of the heterocyclic system². We now report the synthesis and antimicrobial studies of some new fluorinated 2-amino-4-arylthiazoles (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Substituted-2-amino-4-arylthiazoles (3a-h) have been obtained by direct fusion of substituted acetophenones (1a-h), thiourea and iodine³. Ir and nmr data are presented.

In the mass spectrum of 3a (Scheme 2), the parent peak appears at m/z 194, constituting the base peak also and confirms the molecular formula as C₉H₇FN₂S. The high stability can be attributed to the high degree of conjugation present in the molecular ion 1. Under electron impact the molecular ion 1 may decompose following path a and b. In path a, the parent ion may expel a neutral HCN moiety to give the cation radical 2 (m/z 167, 14.4%) which subsequently fragments a CHS radical giving rise to the cation 6 (m/z 122, 87.84%). This in turn expels neutral HCN to give the cation 9 (m/z 95, 34.56%) which may give out a fluorine radical giving rise to the benzyne radical ion 11 (m/z 76, 36%) or eliminate neutral HF to give the benzyne cation 12 (m/z 75, 36%). Alternatively, the molecular ion 1 may eliminate a CHN₂ radical giving rise to the cation 3 (m/z 153, 57.6%) which may expel a neutral CH₂ moiety giving the cation 5 (m/z 139, 15.84%) or a hydrogen radical to give the cation radical 4 (m/z 152, 56.2%). The cation 5 may expel a neutral CS moiety to give the cation 9 (m/z 95, 34.56%) obtained from pathway a also. Further fragmentation of cation radical 4 leads to the formation of

fluorophenylacetylide radical ion 7 (m/z 120, 31.68%) after elimination of neutral S atom. It now loses a neutral C atom and rearranges to the trophylum radical ion 8 (m/z 108, 25.00%). The latter loses a fluorine radical giving cation 10 (m/z 90, 31.56%) which fragments a neutral C₂H₂ forming the cyclopentadiene cation 13 (m/z 64, 36%).

Scheme 2. Mass fragmentation pattern of compound 3a.

Antimicrobial activity: All the compounds (3a-h) were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity following the disc-diffusion method⁴ and activity index calculated⁵. Their minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was also determined by dilution tube method⁶ using streptomycin (for antibacterial) and mycostatin (for antifungal activity) as reference compounds. The test organism were *Aspergillus flavus*, *A. niger*, *Curvularia lunata* and *Fusarium moniliformae* as the fungi and *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* as the bacteria.

Compounds 3a-c, f-h were found active against *A. flavus*, *A. niger* and *C. lunata* while none of the compounds exhibited activity against *Fusarium* sp. Compound 3a exhibited maximum activity (AI = 1.81) by disc-diffusion method. The MIC values of compounds 3a-c, f-h against various

fungi formed in the range 50–100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, whereas **3d** and **e** were totally inactive. Compound **3a** was found to be highly active (MIC, 5.2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$).

None of the compounds was active against *S. aureus* although they exhibited some antibacterial activity against *E. coli* with **3a** (AI = 1.1). The MIC value of **3a** was found to be 10.6 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, whereas no inhibitory action was observed for other compounds.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr (CDCl_3), ^{19}F nmr (CDCl_3) and ^{13}C nmr (DMSO-d_6) spectra on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer using TMS as internal standard for ^1H nmr (89.55 MHz), hexafluorobenzene as external standard for ^{19}F nmr (84.25 MHz) and ^{13}C nmr spectra were recorded at 22.49 MHz, and mass spectra on an MS-30/MS-50 Kratos spectrometer (70 eV). Tlc was done on using silica gel in various solvent systems. All compounds were found homogeneous by tlc when a mixture of benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) was used as the solvent.

3-Chloro-4-fluoroacetophenone, 2-chloro-4-fluoroacetophenone, 3-methoxy-4-fluoroacetophenone and 3,4-difluoroacetophenone were prepared by literature methods⁷. 2-Fluoro-, 2,4-difluoro- and 2,3,4,5,6-pentafluoroacetophenones were commercial products.

2-Amino-4-(2-fluorophenyl)thiazole (3a): A mixture of 2-fluoroacetophenone (0.05 mol), thiourea (0.1 mol) and iodine (0.05 mol) was heated for 60 h at 80–90°. The mass obtained was kept in contact with ether for 24 h. Ether was then decanted off and the solid obtained was washed with a solution of sodium thiosulphate (30%) and finally with water. The residue left was dissolved in boiling water, filtered, cooled and ammonia solution added to it till basic.

The resulting solid was washed and crystallised from benzene as yellow powder : **3a** (74%), m.p. 95–96°; ν_{max} 3 300, 3 400 cm^{-1} (NH_2); ^1H nmr δ 5.02 (s, NH_2), 7.92 (thiazolyl), 6.63–8.04 (ArH); ^{13}C nmr δ 167.833 (C-2'), 146.262 (C-2), 129.695 (C-6'), 129.532 (C-4'), 128.828 (C-4), 124.233 (C-5'), 116.313 (C-1'), 115.282 (C-5), 108.079 (C-3'); ^{19}F nmr δ 113.05 (s); m/z M^+ 194 (100), 167 (14.4), 153 (57.6), 152 (55.2), 139 (15.8), 122 (87.8), 120 (31.6) 108 (25.0), 95 (34.5), 90 (31.5), 76 (36.0), 75 (36.0), 64 (12.7). Other compounds (**3b-h**) were prepared similarly (yields 60–83%), **3b**, m.p. 125–27°; **c**, 131–32°; **d**, 180–82°; **e**, 158–60°; **f**, 122–23°; **g**, 108–09°; **h**, 142–43°. All the compounds gave satisfactory N and S analysis.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. C. Jain, Department of Botany, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, for evaluation of antimicrobial activity and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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